

Use of Fruit Names in Medical Euphemisms and Literary Texts

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Abstract: In this article, the healing power of fruits is classified through their names in various epithets and medicinal herbs through examples taken from works of art. We also think that a single fruit represents both a common symbolic meaning and sometimes a separate symbolic logic in different nations.

Keywords: "Makhzan-ul-adwiya" by Muhammad Husain ibn Muhammad al-Aqili, works of Abu Ali ibn Sina, Z.M. Babur in his work "Baburnoma", Folk oral works, Uzbek poetic texts, Anvar Obidjan, grapes and Pomegranate and apricot and apple and quince and pomegranate and peach and plum and sandalwood and almond and walnut.

Introduction. The unique soil and climate conditions of Uzbekistan, 320 days of sunshine per year on average, and consistent change of four seasons provide a favorable natural opportunity for growing high-quality fruits and vegetables. After all, the agricultural season begins in the first days of March, when new greens ripen naturally, and does not stop, so to speak, throughout the year. That is, yellow fruits will be offered until the beginning of December, when late varieties of grapes, melons, dates and quinces will be delivered to the markets.

According to the experts, the fruits grown in our conditions are rich in natural sugar, amino and organic acids, trace elements necessary for health and various biological substances that cannot be replaced in the food diet. Already, in ancient times, Ibn Sina used fruits and vegetables and various herbs and plants to treat various diseases.

The Main Part

The medicinal properties of fruits are expressed in various ephemeral units and medicinal herbs through their names. Including

Doctors say that apples avoid disease wherever they are, and they recommend apples as a disease-carrying fruit. Because apples have the property of reducing the amount of cholesterol in the blood. Its bark is useful in preventing cancer. It is necessary to try to eat an apple with its peel. By consuming it in this way, quercetin and vitamin C enter the body.

Banana is the fruit of athletes. Because it has the ability to give energy to a person. It is enough to eat two bananas for an hour and a half of non-stop exercise on the sports field. Research shows this. It contains vitamin B6, which normalizes blood glucose levels and improves mood. Banana helps in anemia. Potassium improves heart function and water balance in the body.

Chilonjiydi is a huge tree that is 2.5 to 6 meters tall and belongs to the jumrut family. The grainy, round or elongated fruit ripens in September. It has been valued as a unique blessing

since ancient times. This is evidenced by the fact that two thousand years ago in medicine, a number of diseases were treated with the help of a plumber¹.

According to Muhammad Husain ibn Muhammad al-Aqili's book "Makhzan-ul-Adwiya", quince relieves headaches, strengthens the heart, improves the work of the liver and stomach, increases appetite, and removes bad breath. It is also useful for diarrhea, diarrhea, and jaundice. It also prevents unpleasant bleeding in the body. After all, quince is the king of gardens.

According to the great doctor Abu Ali ibn Sina, if the juice of a walnut leaf is dripped into the ear while it is warm, suppuration will be prevented. The condensed juice of the bark relieves sore throats and coughs. If the roasted one is placed on the navel, it suppresses intestinal pains and stops diarrhea... According to Ibn Sina, walnut is a fruit that cures a thousand ailments.

Z.M. Babur writes in his work "Boburnoma": "Another Margilandur is located in the west of Andijan, Andijandin is seven miles away. May a good life happen, a pure blessing; Pomegranates and harvests are many - it will be fine. It is a kind of pomegranate, they say "one big one", and when it is sweet, it has a taste like sour cream. It is possible to visit the Samnan pomegranates. I'm going to eat another kind of sorghum, they take a grain, put the seeds in it and dry it, they call it "subhani", it's delicious."

The historical and cultural heritage left by His Holiness Baburshah and his descendants continues to amaze the peoples of the world. Hazrat Babur writes again: "Kabul province is the fourth climate." Grapes, pomegranates, apricots, apples, quinces, pomegranates, peaches, plums, sandalwood, almonds, and walnuts are among the sardine fruits in Kabul and Kent. I brought and planted plum seedlings, there were good plums and they were still growing. Garmseri fruits such as oranges and oranges and amluk and cane sugar La omonottin bring. Kabul's rivuhi is good, bihi bila aluli is also good. Cucumber is good too. There is a type of grape, called obi angur, and it is a very good grape. There will be drunken calls. Khwaja Howard Saeed Domani is famous throughout the country. If they describe imitation and tradition as follows: "*Lazzati may mast donad hushyoronro chi haz*"².

The use of fruit names as symbols in folklore and Uzbek poetic texts has been around for a long time. For example, an apple is a symbol of love, a pomegranate is a symbol of fidelity to marriage, etc.

Poem called "pomegranate" from Uvaysi

*Ul na gumbazdur eshigi tuynugidin yo 'q nishon,
Necha gulgunpo 'sh qizlar manzil aylabdur makon.
Sindirub gumbazni alar holidin olsam xabar,
Yuzlarida parda tortig 'liq tururlar bag 'ri qon.*

Through this chiston, Uvaysi compared the pomegranate to the tender girls whose faces are covered with veils inside the dome. Today, in Uzbek children's literature, the literary puzzle "Pomegranate" created by Anvar Obidjon is distinguished by the fact that it does not repeat any aspect of it:

*Har donacham bir askar,
Bir qal'ada ming lashkar.
Yotar ular panada,
Oq pardali xonada.*

¹ Ma'lumotlar <https://zarnews.uz/> dan olindi.

² Bobur Zahiriddin Muhammad. Boburnoma. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2018. – B.698.

Xonalar tinch, atrof jim.

Qal'achani buzsa kim,

Boshlanadi to 'polon...

U yog 'i sizga ayon.

Poet Anvar Obidjon compares pomegranate seeds to soldiers. They express that they will not look at anyone who disturbs their peace and damages their fortress. According to some sources, pomegranate is derived from the Latin word "granatum", "granatus" and is a grain, according to the many seeds inside the fruit, it is surrounded by a watery cover.

Apple is a symbol of love. Apple is a symbol of salvation. Apple is a symbol of eternal harmony. Apple-cosmic symbol, etc.

So, a single fruit can express both the meaning of a common symbol and sometimes the logic of a separate symbol in different peoples. Including

Apple is a symbol of love, as well as a symbol of temptation, the fall of man and salvation; The Celts believed in the golden apple of eternal youth, and among the Chinese, the gift of an apple embodies the idea of eternal harmony. For the Slavs, it served as a sign of love; the young man and the girl openly declared their love by exchanging apples with each other. Because of its almost perfect round shape, the apple is considered a cosmic symbol, so kings and queens hold the sovereign apple (power) in their hands, which represents the whole world along with the scepter. (<https://uz.info-4all.ru/>)

*Baland shoxda **qizil olma** pishgan ekan,*

*Uzib olib qaragam, **qurt tushgan** ekan.*

Men olmani irg'itvorsam, u dod soldi,

Tashlab ketar ekan meni nega oldi? (M.Yusuf)

A red apple with a worm on it is a symbol of a girl deceived in love.

When I don't remember

I remembered your apples and pomegranates. (From the song Khorazm)

The apple and pomegranate in the song are symbols of the beautiful face of the lover.

Fruit is a child, a symbol of love.

... may the light of our eyes, the strength of our backs, the fruit of our life reach our son Mullah Otabek and be known and enlightened. and we are praying for the soul of the light of our eyes to be healthy in the morning and evening, but also from the Almighty Rabbulolamin. (A. Qadiri. Past days. p. 35)

The fruit of man is a child. (Proverbs)

Mother - tree, child - fruit. (Proverbs)

Love is the fruit of the heart. (Proverbs)

The fruit tree was considered a symbol of the goddess of fertility in the peoples of the world until the recent past.

A fruit tree is a symbol of a woman with a child.

Thank you, mother and daughter - a fruit tree. A full-skirted boy.

A fruit tree is a symbol of a scientist practicing his knowledge.

Learn. Along with knowledge, acquire calmness, dignity and hilm (gentleness). Be humble to the person teaching you. Let those who learn from you also be humble. A man of knowledge who follows his knowledge is like a fruit tree. Do not be one of the oppressive scholars. Don't let your knowledge overshadow your ignorance. (Ali ibn Abu Talib)

A fruitless tree is a symbol of childlessness.

- So... you are good... You are a very good person! To make a good person like you live with a fruitless tree like me... After all... after all, there is no place we haven't been to, right? No one gave us hope. Everyone believes that I can't have children except you.
- No, remember what dad said. They say everything is from Allah, be patient! (Z. Mirzayeva. Mysterious confidant)

A person without children is a tree without fruit. (Proverbs)

A fruitless tree is a symbol of ignorance or lack of knowledge. Knowledge without practice is like a tree without fruit. (Hadith) Ibn Raslan al-Shafi'i says in the preface of his collection of poetry entitled "Az-Zabad":

A scientist does not follow his knowledge,

Before the idolater, there will be punishment.

Our great enlightened grandfather Abdulla Avloni said: "Knowledge is the path, life, leader and salvation of people. Knowledge is a very high holy quality for a person. Because it sharpens our mind and thoughts like a sword, a person without knowledge is like a tree without fruit.

A person without knowledge is like a tree without fruit. Prophet Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace, compared knowledge to the fruit of faith and said: "Faith is a naked thing, its clothing is piety, its adornment is modesty, and its fruit is knowledge."

Without understanding all the rules of fasting, following it blindly is like a tree without fruit. Islam is a religion of knowledge, and every Muslim man and woman must learn what is beneficial and harmful for him. (D. Nurmuhammad. Are you ready for Ramadan?)

If life was wasted, it means that a person could not do good deeds. It did not benefit people and society. To waste time is to live like a fruitless tree. (T. Malik. Property of humanity)

A fruitless tree is a symbol of generosity or recklessness.

An ungenerous person is a spring without rain and a muskrat without a plan. A tree without fruit is still wood, and a cloud without rain is still smoke. There is a judgment for a person without a heart and a heart without a gem. What is the attention of those who die without care.

Conclusion

It seems that in the religion of Islam and related hadiths and educational texts, ignorance, non-practice of knowledge or generosity are likened to a fruitless tree.

The names of fruits are noteworthy in that they serve to justify the integration of linguistics with knowledge related to natural sciences, in particular, the world of flora and fauna, the connection between society and nature, society and literature. In particular, the world of fruits, which are part of it, occupy a special position through the depiction in fiction, a traditional poetic image, sometimes used as a symbol of stability or situation, it is observed at the level of phytopoetonym, it is widely used in giving a human image, poetic expression and evaluation of personal qualities. are directly noteworthy aspects.

In conclusion, it can be said that the image of fruits is often used in fiction to poetically express human characteristics, personal beauty, or some aspect of it. Then the lexical-semantic signs

of the name of fruits in language and speech, nominative-motivational bases are clearly visible. Studying them from this point of view helps to understand the place of fruit names in the language, their lexical system and structure, their use and enrichment in connection with the people's living area, national-cultural life, lifestyle.

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